

REINVENTING THE POPULAR MEANING OF DEMOCRACY IN THE TIMES OF CRISIS IN EUROPEAN PERIPHERY

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JANEZ ŠTEBE

FDV and ADP, University of Ljubljana

Popular Understanding of Democracy

- Why it is important?

- Democracy is a political system which provides conditions for societal decision-making among conflicting social groups under specific conditions of „**system of beliefs**, legitimising the democratic system“ (Lipset 1959: 71)

- „Democracy is not achieved by act of will alone; but men`s wills, through action, can shape institutions and events in directions that reduce or increase the chance of the development and survival of democracy“. (Ibid.)

- Becoming of democracy through meaning attached to it...

Meaning of Democracy

PERCEIVED MEANINGS OF DEMOCRACY IN SLOVENIA, 2005 AND 2011

^a Many things are desirable, but not all of them are essential characteristics of democracy. Please tell me for each of the following things how essential you think it is as a characteristic of democracy. Use this scale where 1 means "not at all an essential characteristic of democracy" and 10 means it definitely is "an essential characteristic of democracy". Source: Toš and group., 2011 based on WVS Questionnaire

PRINCIPLE COMPONENT ANALYSIS OF THE PERCEIVED MEANINGS OF DEMOCRACY, SLOVENIA 2011 (Source: Toš et al., 2011).

<p><i>Many things are desirable, but not all of them are essential characteristics of democracy. Please tell me for each of the following things how essential you think it is as a characteristic of democracy. Use this scale where 1 means "not at all an essential characteristic of democracy" and 10 means it definitely is "an essential characteristic of democracy". (WVS 2012 module)</i></p>	Component			
	1	2	3	4
Women have the same rights as men.	0,81	0,10	0,04	0,10
Civil rights protect people from state oppression.	0,77	0,32	0,13	0,01
People choose their leaders in free elections.	0,72	0,03	-0,05	0,41
Governments tax the rich and subsidize the poor.	0,12	0,90	-0,03	0,16
The state makes people's incomes equal.	0,32	0,62	0,44	0,05
People obey their rulers.	0,02	0,06	0,95	0,11
People receive state aid for unemployment.	0,19	0,17	0,13	0,92
Cumulative %	27	47	63	78

A choice of dependent variable

- To test

- how the two components of meaning of democracy affects legitimacy

- "While effectiveness is primarily instrumental, legitimacy **is evaluative**. Groups regard a political system as legitimate or illegitimate to the way in which **its values fit with theirs**."* (Lipset 1981/1984)

- We choose support as containing evaluative dimension (in contrast to satisfaction with functioning)

- Support for democracy index is made of this items:

- "I'm going to describe various types of political systems and ask what you think about each as a way of governing this country. For each one, would you say it is a very good, fairly good, fairly bad or very bad way of governing this country?"

- Having a democratic political system ,,

- and inverse of

- "--- Having a strong leader...,,

- and

- "How important is it for you to live in a country that is governed democratically?"

I'm going to describe various types of political systems and ask what you think about each as a way of governing this country. For each one, would you say it is a very good, fairly good, fairly bad or very bad way of governing this country? (% very good+fairly good)

Source: Toš and group, 2011.

Hypothesis

Liberal component will prevail in generating a support for democracy due to congruence of citizens' values and meaning of ,ideal` object of support;

Social Justice component: support for democracy based on values of equality will be more ambivalent (between demands based on self-interests and common interests that values regarding democracy would ideally contain);

In a context of group of countries in East European periphery, where values of equality are dominant, and constant pressure towards social benefits reduction is present, an effect would be negative

Protests in Ljubljana, 30.11.2012

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Slovenia says reforms on track despite ratings downgrade

Slovenia on Saturday said it was confident its newly-adopted action plan would stabilise public finances and lead to an economic recovery, a day after international ratings agency Fitch downgraded the crisis-hit

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PREDICTORS OF THE SUPPORT FOR DEMOCRACY (OLS regression, standardised coefficients, significant are bold typed)

	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4
<i>Meaning of democracy</i>				
Liberal	0,39	0,33	0,32	0,3
Social	-0,12	-0,06	-0,05	-0,06
<i>Values</i>				
Equality (redistribution)		-0,09	-0,09	-0,06
Equality (vs. Merit)		-0,06	-0,04	0
Equality (vs. liberal-capitalist)		-0,02	-0,02	0
Liberal morality		0,05	0,02	0,06
Gender equality		0,18	0,15	0,12
<i>Social identities group of variables</i>			(…)	
<i>Assessments of the social conditions group of variables</i>			(…)	
R2	0,12	0,18	0,21	0,26

For comparison, the same variables as PREDICTORS OF THE SATISFACTION WITH DEMOCRACY

R2	0,01	0,07	0,13	0,48
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	West Germany	Spain	Norway	Sweden	Finland	Poland	East Germany	Slovenia	Bulgaria	Romania	Serbia
Model 1											
Meaning of democracy: Liberal	0,46 ***	0,52 ***	0,34 ***	0,50 ***	0,58 ***	0,48 ***	0,29 ***	0,44 ***	0,40 ***	0,31 ***	0,66 ***
- Social	0,08 *	0,07 *	0,09 **	0,02	0,01	-0,10 *	0,01	-0,07	0,04	-0,12 **	-0,15 ***
Model 2											
Meaning of democracy: Liberal	0,36 ***	0,42 ***	0,23 ***	0,42 ***	0,50 ***	0,41 ***	0,21 ***	0,32 ***	0,40 ***	0,28 ***	0,59 ***
- Social	0,11 **	0,04	0,06 *	0,03	0,01	-0,03	0,03	-0,02	0,04	-0,05	-0,15 ***
Equality (vs. Merit)	-0,08 *	0,08 *	0,07 *	-0,01	0,08 *	-0,02	0,09 *	-0,07	0,09	0,02	-0,11 **
Equality (vs. liberal-capitalist)	-0,05	-0,05	-0,03	-0,03	0,00	-0,14 ***	-0,02	-0,16 ***	-0,14 **	-0,20 ***	0,05
Equality (redistribution)	-0,07	0,07	-0,01	0,05	-0,02	-0,06	-0,09 *	0,01	-0,03	-0,07	-0,06
Gender equality	0,11 **	0,11 **	0,14 ***	0,09 **	0,09 **	0,06	0,12 ***	0,22 ***	0,03	0,03	0,06
Liberal morality	0,13 ***	0,13 ***	0,11 ***	0,05	0,10 **	0,12 **	0,04	0,05	0,05	0,15 ***	-0,04
Living conditions	0,08 *	-0,02	0,00	0,01	0,03	-0,06	-0,04	0,04	0,02	-0,03	0,07
Individual material condition	-0,02	0,04	-0,04	0,01	0,01	0,01	0,12 **	0,03	0,05	0,08	0,05
Generalised trust	0,09 **	-0,03	0,14 ***	0,03	0,01	0,13 **	0,06	0,05	0,00	0,03	0,07 *
Human rights (respected)	0,14 ***	0,07 *	0,21 ***	0,04	0,13 ***	0,05	0,15 ***	0,09 *	0,06	0,10 **	0,05
Education (university)	0,08 *	-0,04	0,17 ***	0,13 ***	0,06	0,09 *	0,02	0,08	0,12 **	-0,01	0,00
Political orientation (right)	-0,13 ***	-0,09 **	0,00	-0,03	-0,08 **	-0,03	-0,12 ***	0,03	0,08	0,01	0,09 **
Gender (female)	-0,02	0,00	-0,01	-0,04	-0,01	0,01	-0,02	-0,03	0,00	-0,08 *	-0,06
Age	0,06	-0,01	0,12 ***	0,02	0,04	0,07	0,10 **	0,21 ***	-0,04	0,06	-0,02
R2 Model 1 / Model 2	.24/.35	.30/.36	.13/.31	.25/.28	.34/.39	.22/.30	.08/.17	.18/.31	.17/.22	.11/.22	.35/.42

MAKING OF DEMOCRACY

- The strong, unconditional, effect of a liberal procedural understanding based on congruence of meaning, together with gender equality values, serves as a stabilising factor for the functioning of the regime.

SEARCHING FOR DEMOCRACY

- Understanding of democracy based on egalitarian values is indeed more self-interested – in times of cuts in social benefits support is expressed in a negative sense, as a demand directed toward political system for giving insurance against an insecure future;
- A trap of conflicting demands authorities are faced with:
 - Redistribution vs. Economic, Financial, Budgetary efficiency and accountability;
 - Even more social protests activities are likely to occur if scepticism about democratic political system is widespread
 - Deficit in Legitimacy of decision making – Institutional reforms needed?
- Future work...

Background literature

- Lipset, Seymour Martin (1959): Some Social Requisites of Democracy: Economic Development and Political Legitimacy. *American Political Science Review* 53 (1): 632-42.
- Lipset, Seymour Martin (1981/1984): Social Conflict, Legitimacy, and Democracy. In William Connolly (Ed.), *Legitimacy and the State*, 88-103. Oxford: Basil Blackwell.
- Štebe, Janez (2012): Support for Democracy and Meanings of Democracy: Equality and Freedom. *Teorija in praksa*. Vol. 49, No 3, 2012, pp. 516-543
- Toš, Niko, et al. (2011). Slovensko javno mnenje 2011/2: Svetovna raziskava vrednot (WVS) in Ogledalo javnega mnenja [data file]. Slovenija, Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, Center za raziskovanje javnega mnenja in množičnih komunikacij [producer]. Slovenija, Ljubljana: Univerza v Ljubljani, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov [distributor], 2012 forthcoming.
- World Values Survey Association (2005/2009): WORLD VALUES SURVEY 2005 OFFICIAL DATA FILE v.20090901, 2009. World Values Survey Association (www.worldvaluessurvey.org). Madrid: ASEP/JDS